

The environmental and economic impacts of the decarbonization of the steel production in Brazil

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Executive summary

This research explores the transition of the Brazilian steel industry to a low-carbon economy through the analysis of two scenarios: one incorporating existing technologies and another leveraging hydrogen for enhanced emissions mitigation. Results indicate a potential 80% and 90% reduction in emissions, respectively, accompanied by positive economic impacts. Both scenarios foresee increased employment (300-333k jobs) and a rise in GDP (0.28%-0.32%). The study underscores the feasibility of achieving substantial emission reductions with available technologies, contributing crucial insights for policy formulation. The necessity of instruments like carbon pricing, infrastructure investment, and research and development is highlighted to facilitate this transition. Overall, the research emphasizes the positive synergy between environmental goals and economic growth in the pursuit of a net-zero economy.

1. Introduction

The increase of the global temperature is reaching 1.5°C when compared to the pre-industrial levels, a threshold set by the 2015 Paris Agreement. The agreement set the objective of reducing the emissions levels to limit the global warming to less than 2°C and make efforts to limit up to 1.5°C (UNFCCC, 2015).

The steel industry contributes to 7% of the global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. This material is essential to our society: it is used to build our homes, our cars, and the power technologies like solar panels and wind turbines. With the tendency of increasing the demand the steel, the sector has the challenge to supply its demand while reducing its emissions. The difficulty arises considering the difficulty to change the technology of steel production. The use of less carbon intensive energy sources requires the transformation of the entire industry facility and will impact the upstream sectors (IEA, 2020).

There are many studies regarding the decarbonization of the steel industry (IPCC, 2023). However, one question that needs to be answered is how the change of the profile of the steel industry will impact the whole economy and the environment. In this sense, this research will provide a first step in investigating these impacts using an environmental expanded input-output table analysis.

2. Methodology

The method for analyzing the impacts of changing the steel production in Brazil uses the input-output tables (IOT). The input-output tables can be described as a snapshot of the economy, depicting the relationships between economic sectors through the flows of goods and services. These tables can be extended by adding multi regions to amplify the scope of the interdependence in the whole economy, as within a country by adding its states or provinces, or even the world by adding other countries. Also, the tables can be extended by adding environmental inputs and outputs (Guilhoto, 2011).

There are several databases for IOT (Maia & Pereira, 2021). In this study, I chose to use the Exiobase, a multi-region IOT. By using this database, it will be possible to analyze the impacts of the decarbonization in the steel industry not only in Brazil but also in other countries.

For the analysis, I used the Multi-functional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO) tool. This is an analytical tool for facilitating the building input-output models based on Python programming language (Tahavor, et al., 2023).

The Figure 1 outlines the key steps of this research. Given that the primary objective is to comprehend the economic and environmental impacts of mitigation technologies in the steel sector, the initial step involves describing these new technologies within the IOT. As the IOT shows the relationship between the goods and services provided by economic activities, new ones are not presented in the tables.

Figure 1 - Diagram of the methodology
Source: the author.

The technologies considered in this study were Direct Reduction (DR) with natural gas (NG), DR with green hydrogen (DR – H₂), Blast Furnace – Basic Oxygen Furnace (BF-BOF) with charcoal and Electric Arc Furnace (EAF). This selection was based on their relevance for reducing emissions in the Brazilian steel industry, as indicated by Hebeda et al. (2023). These technologies are not present in the Exiobase. So, the data regarding the goods supply by region, *i.e.*, which countries sells to Brazil the main commodities for producing steel had to be implemented in the model.

The subsequent step involves defining the production shocks to comprehend the ensuing environmental and economic impacts. For this purpose, two scenarios were established for the transformation of the technological profile of steel production in Brazil (see Table 1). These scenarios draw inspiration from prior studies on the decarbonization of the Brazilian steel industry (Hebeda, et al., 2023) The first scenario considers a shift in the steel industry profile through the adoption of currently available technologies. In contrast, the second scenario, characterized by a more ambitious mitigation goal, necessitates the use of advanced technologies like hydrogen to achieve emission reductions.

Table 1 - Scenario share of steel technologies

Technology	Baseline	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
BF-BOF coal	69%	7%	7%
EAF	24%	37%	37%
BF-BOF charcoal	7%	36%	36%
DR-NG	0%	24%	0

DR-H2	0%	0	24%
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Source: the author.

3. Results

In this section, we will show the results regarding the environmental and economic impacts of the two scenarios designed to analyze the decarbonization of the steel production in Brazil. The environmental impacts encompass the greenhouse gas emissions in the steel industry as well as in the other sectors and regions that may be affected by profile changes. Meanwhile, the economic impacts provide insights into changes in GDP and labor.

Regarding the emissions, the results show a reduction of 44 MtCO₂ in the in the Scenario 1 when compared to the base line (Figure 2). The reduction of the production of steel by BF-BOF technology is replaced by the increase of production by BF-BOF charcoal, EAF and DR-NG. In this way, the emissions of BF-BOF decreased by -57 MtCO₂ while the emissions of DR-NG increased by 11 MtCO₂. These are the main factors for the differences that impacts the emissions. Besides, also there is the increase in the energy emissions and some residuals increases in other sectors.

In Scenario 2, the reduction in emissions is even more substantial. BF-BOF declined 61 MtCO₂. The main difference in this scenario lies in the use of H₂ instead of NG. This leads to a slight increase in the energy emissions due the higher demand of electricity. However, given the predominantly renewable nature of the Brazilian energy system, the increase in emissions from the energy sector is less than the emissions increase observed in DR-NG in the previous scenario.

Figure 2 - Reduction in the emissions of the Brazilian steel industry in the two scenarios

Source: the author

Concerning the economic impacts, we can see the difference in the number of employees between the scenarios analyzed in Figure 3. In Scenario 1 there is an increase of over 400k jobs in the Brazilian economy (Figure 3). This surge is primarily observed in alternative steel technologies such as DR, BF-BOF with charcoal, and EAF, reflecting their increased share in steel production. Additionally, there is also an increase in other industry sectors and agriculture, due the increase of charcoal used in the steel industry. However, there is a corresponding decrease in jobs in the traditional steel production route using mineral coal, resulting in a net increase of 305k jobs.

The Scenario 2, where the main difference is the use of hydrogen technology to achieve higher emission mitigation, indicates that the number of jobs will increase by 333k. This value, higher than scenario 1 by almost 10%, can be justified by the increase in the number of workers in steel sector, specifically in the DR – H2 technology and in other sectors related to the hydrogen industry.

Figure 3 - Jobs changes in the Brazilian economy in scenario 1 and 2

Source: the author

Moreover, the change in the steel industry profile, from a fossil fuel technology to renewable energy will have a positive impact in the national GDP (Table 2). In Scenario 1, the results show an increase of 0.28% in the GDP. While in scenario 2 the increase in GDP was 0.32%, higher than Scenario 1.

Table 2 - GDP variation among the scenarios

Scenario	GDP variation
Scenario 1	0.28%
Scenario 2	0.32%

Source: the author.

4. Discussion

In this section, I will discuss the main implications of the results regarding the transformation of the steel industry profile.

One noteworthy insight from the results provide is regarding to the impacts on the level of emissions in other sectors. The current structure of the Brazilian industry relies mostly in the use of BF-BOF with mineral coal. The transition from this technology to DR with NG, and the increase of other traditional technologies like BF-BOF charcoal and EAF is expected to

raise emissions levels in other sectors, particularly in the energy sector. However, this increase constitutes less than 2% of the emissions mitigated by the adoption of alternative technologies, primarily due to the high proportion of renewables in the Brazilian energy sector.

This represents a competitive advantage of Brazil when compared to other countries. In other main steel producers' countries, like China and India, the electricity generation is based on fossil fuels like coal. As Brazil has one of the most renewable energy sectors in the world, Brazil can produce low carbon steel without increase its overall emissions.

An additional advantage of the Brazilian steel industry decarbonization is the possibility of achieving high level emission reduction with mature technologies. The scenario 1 indicates that the Brazilian steel industry has the potential to mitigate almost 80% with most of the mitigation coming from EAF and BF-BOFC charcoal. This an advantage in comparison to other countries that does not have the same availability low carbon energy resources like charcoal and low carbon electricity. As in Scenario 2 the use of hydrogen replaces the natural gas to increase the level of GHG mitigation. Despite being two different technologies, the DR with NG can be retrofitted into H2 with low cost. This indicates that the Scenario 1 can be an intermediate step to the Brazilian steel industry between the industry.

The economic impacts analyzed in this study also shows a positive effect in the level of employment and in the GDP, as the transition of the steel industry will replace the imports of energy source (coal) to the use of national renewable energy. This finding is contrary to the empirical sense that shows the decarbonization may have a negative impact on the economic activity (CNI, 2018).

From the results, the decarbonization of the steel industry must overcome some barriers. The change from a technology to another is not easy. First, they have higher cost than the traditional ones. To support this transition, carbon price mechanism are essential to equate the prices between low carbon technologies and the high emission ones. Also, despite the high potential of renewable source that Brazil has, the use of charcoal and electricity will require investment in infrastructure to connect the steel facilities to the energy source. This can be difficult to overcome considering the size of Brazil, the fifth largest country in the

world. Another barrier that must be overcome is the investment in research and development. The direct reduction with hydrogen technology is still in development with few countries using it and in pilot facilities.

The analyzes provided by this research has some limitations. First, it used a global database. The advantage is that can provide information between the interactions, not within the national economy, but as well with other regions. However, the data can be improved to get results more suitable to the Brazilian reality. Also, the information regarding new technologies there are few data available of the raw materials requirements for producing steel and its feasibility.

The analysis made in this study opens the opportunity to investigate other aspects of the industry decarbonization. Despite the importance of studying the mitigation potential of the steel production profile, it is necessary to analyze how demand side measures can contribute to the reduction of the emissions in the industry. Material efficiency in buildings, lightweighting vehicles and consumers change can reduce the consumption of raw materials, like steel, and so, reduce the emissions in the sector. Another potential area for future research is regarding the level of investment required, not in the steel industry, but in the other sectors that support the transition. For example, as mentioned in the previous section, the use of technologies as DR with Hydrogen will require a transportation system, and so, investments must be made to make this option available. Considering the framework created by this research, other studies can be created to understand future scenarios with different levels of demand. Also, it is possible to analyze the impacts of changing the profile of the steel industry in other countries to see the impacts on the emissions and in the economy among the sectors.

5. Conclusion

The present research aimed to analyze the transition of the steel industry towards a low-carbon economy. Utilizing Input-Output Tables (IOT) supported by MARIO, we assessed the environmental and economic impacts of this technological shift. Two scenarios were created—one based on well-known technologies and another incorporating DR – H2 for enhanced emissions mitigation.

The results indicate that Brazil can reduce the emissions by 80% using only technologies already available for the industry, and it can achieve a reduction of 90% when using hydrogen. Also, the emission reduction comes with positive impacts on the economy. In both scenarios there are an increase in the level of employment in Brazil between 300 to 333k. With this, the GDP of the country increased by 0.28% and 0.32%.

With these results, the study contributes for the formulation of industrial policies providing important insights. The transition will not occur without instruments to direct the investments. Carbon prices mechanisms are necessary to level the cost of technologies; investment in infrastructure and in research and development also will be needed to enable the use of technologies, both the mature and the innovative ones.

In essence, the study demonstrates that the path to a net-zero economy can have positive outcomes for both the environment and the economy. However, further research is essential to explore the interplay between the transition of the steel industry and demand-side measures, as well as the global impacts of economic and environmental changes in steel decarbonization.

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